

MEDICAL SCIENCES

TRENDS IN CANCER-RELATED AND UNKNOWN-CAUSE MORTALITY IN GEORGIA, 2013-2023

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Abstract

Accurate mortality data are essential for cancer control and health planning. This retrospective registry-based ecological study analyzed aggregated annual mortality data from Georgia's national death registry for 2013–2023, focusing on cancer-related deaths and deaths attributed to unknown causes. A strong negative correlation was observed between the proportional share of cancer-related deaths and unknown-cause deaths ($R = -0.725$; $R^2 = 0.525$; $F = 9.95$; $p = 0.012$). The findings suggest that the recorded decline in cancer mortality should be interpreted cautiously, as it may partly reflect limitations in cause-of-death certification, documentation, or mortality reporting. Improved registry validation and standardized death certification are needed.

Keywords: cancer mortality, unknown causes of death, mortality reporting, death certification, Georgia.

BACKGROUND

Cancer remains one of the major global health challenges. According to the World Health Organization [1], approximately 20 million new cancer cases and 9.7 million cancer-related deaths were reported in 2022, while 53.5 million people were living within five years after a cancer diagnosis. WHO estimates that about one in five people will develop cancer during their lifetime, and approximately one in nine men and one in twelve women will die from the disease [2]. Despite this burden, access to cancer care remains uneven: only 39% of countries include essential cancer treatment in guaranteed health benefit packages, and only 28% provide coverage for patients requiring palliative support, including pain relief [2].

Globally, lung, breast, and colorectal cancers were the most common cancers in 2022, while lung cancer remained the leading cause of cancer death, followed by colorectal, liver, breast, and stomach cancers [2]. Future projections suggest that the cancer burden will continue to rise. By 2050, more than 35 million new cancer cases are expected worldwide, representing a 77% increase compared with 2022. This increase is largely driven by population aging, population growth, changes in major risk factors such as tobacco use, alcohol consumption, obesity, and environmental exposures, including air pollution. The proportional increase is expected to be greatest in low- and medium-HDI countries, where cancer deaths are projected to nearly double by 2050 [3; 2].

Monitoring cancer outcomes and mortality statistics is, therefore, a key public health priority. Accurate registration of cancer-related deaths provides essential information on disease burden, mortality trends, treatment effectiveness, and health system performance. Such data are necessary for epidemiological research,

policy development, resource allocation, and prevention planning. Cancer registry data are particularly important for monitoring changes in cancer incidence and mortality, evaluating cancer control activities, identifying service gaps, and supporting evidence-based public health strategies [4].

Population aging further increases the importance of reliable cancer and palliative care data. By 2050, the global population aged 60 years and older is expected to reach 2 billion, increasing the prevalence of chronic and life-limiting conditions and placing additional pressure on health systems. The United Nations Sustainable Development Goals and global palliative care frameworks emphasize that universal health coverage should include promotion, prevention, treatment, rehabilitation, and palliative care. WHO's healthy aging strategy also highlights the need to adapt health systems to the needs of older adults, provide long-term integrated care, and ensure multiple access points to services [5; 6].

Palliative care plays an important role in addressing the comprehensive needs of cancer patients by providing relief from physical symptoms and offering psychological, social, and spiritual support. Effective palliative care requires a multidisciplinary approach, specialized training, and continuous professional development. Palliative care education programs can improve access to and use of services by strengthening competencies in symptom management, communication, and end-of-life care. Awareness campaigns and educational initiatives may also reduce stigma and support earlier integration of palliative care. According to ASCO recommendations, palliative care should be introduced as early as possible alongside active cancer treatment, rather than being limited to the end of life [7; 8]

In Georgia, the adequacy and quality of palliative care services remain insufficiently documented. Although global cancer mortality continues to rise, national data indicate that cancer-related deaths in Georgia decreased between 2013 and 2023. This pattern raises questions about the accuracy and completeness of death registration, particularly if the decline in recorded cancer mortality occurs alongside an increase in deaths attributed to unknown causes. Understanding this relationship is important for evaluating mortality reporting, identifying potential gaps in diagnostic accuracy, and informing the development of coordinated and multidisciplinary palliative care services in Georgia.

AIM

The aim of this study was to analyze mortality trends in Georgia from 2013 to 2023, with a specific focus on cancer-related deaths and deaths attributed to unknown causes. The study also assessed the share of cancer mortality in total mortality and examined the relationship between the proportional share of cancer-related deaths and deaths registered under unknown causes.

METHODS

Study Design

This study used a retrospective registry-based ecological design to examine mortality trends in Georgia from 2013 to 2023. The analysis focused on annual changes in cancer-related mortality and deaths attributed to unknown causes.

Data Source

Mortality data were obtained from Georgia's national death registry for the period 2013–2023 [9]. The dataset included aggregated annual mortality indicators, including the total number of deaths, deaths attributed to cancer, and deaths registered as due to unknown causes. Mid-year population estimates were used to calculate crude cancer mortality rates.

Variables and Measures

The primary variables were annual deaths attributed to cancer and annual deaths attributed to unknown causes. Cancer mortality was assessed using the annual number of cancer-related deaths, the crude cancer mortality rate per 100,000 population, and the proportional share of cancer-related deaths among total deaths.

The crude cancer mortality rate was calculated using the following formula:

$$\text{Crude cancer mortality rate} = (\text{Number of cancer deaths} / \text{Mid-year population}) \times 100,000$$

The share of cancer mortality in total mortality was calculated as:

$$\text{Cancer mortality share} = (\text{Number of cancer deaths} / \text{Total deaths}) \times 100$$

The share of deaths attributed to unknown causes was calculated as:

$$\text{Unknown-cause mortality share} = (\text{Number of deaths attributed to unknown causes} / \text{Total deaths}) \times 100$$

Deaths attributed to unknown causes were analyzed as an indicator of potential gaps in cause-of-death documentation and mortality reporting.

Statistical Analysis

Descriptive trend analysis was conducted to examine annual changes in cancer mortality and deaths attributed to unknown causes during the study period. Both crude mortality rates and proportional mortality shares were examined to describe mortality patterns over time.

Pearson correlation analysis was performed to assess the relationship between the proportional share of deaths due to cancer and the proportional share of deaths attributed to unknown causes. This approach was used to evaluate whether years with lower shares of recorded cancer-related deaths were associated with higher shares of deaths registered under unknown causes.

The Pearson correlation coefficient (R) was used to evaluate the strength and direction of the association, while the coefficient of determination (R²) was calculated to estimate the proportion of variation statistically shared between the two indicators. Statistical significance was assessed using an F-test, and a p-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Ethical Considerations

The study was based on aggregated annual registry data and did not include individual-level patient information or personal identifiers. Therefore, individual informed consent was not required.

RESULTS

The analysis demonstrated a strong negative correlation between the share of deaths due to cancer and the share of deaths attributed to unknown causes during the period 2013–2023. The Pearson correlation coefficient was **R = -0.725**, indicating that lower proportions of deaths recorded as due to cancer were associated with higher proportions of deaths registered under unknown causes.

The coefficient of determination was **R² = 0.525**, suggesting that approximately **52.5% of the variation** in one indicator was statistically associated with variation in the other. This finding indicates a notable inverse relationship between the proportional share of cancer-related deaths and deaths attributed to unknown causes over the study period.

The association was statistically significant, as confirmed by the F-test (**F = 9.95; p = 0.012**). This result suggests that the observed inverse relationship was unlikely to be due solely to random variation.

Table 1 presents the annual proportional shares of cancer-related deaths and deaths attributed to unknown causes in Georgia from 2013 to 2023. The findings indicate that the recorded decline in the share of cancer-related deaths occurred alongside an increase in deaths attributed to unknown causes. This inverse pattern may reflect limitations in diagnostic accuracy, cause-of-death certification, or mortality reporting; however, due to the ecological design of the study, causal conclusions cannot be drawn.

Table 1.

The proportional share of cancer-related deaths and deaths attributed to unknown causes in Georgia by years, 2013–2023.

Year	Death due to Cancer	Death due to Unknown causes
2013	9.2%	28.6%
2014	10.3%	35.6%
2015	11.5%	29.4%
2016	11.6%	24.2%
2017	12.8%	27.1%
2018	12.8%	12.3%
2019	13.5%	33.1%
2020	14.8%	22.1%
2021	15.8%	14.9%
2022	16.0%	12.8%
2023	16.9%	13.2%

DISCUSSION

The present study examined cancer-related mortality trends in Georgia between 2013 and 2023 and identified a notable inverse pattern between the recorded share of cancer-related deaths and deaths attributed to unknown causes. The strong negative correlation observed in the analysis ($R = -0.725$) suggests that the decline in recorded cancer mortality occurred in parallel with an increase in deaths registered under unknown causes. Although this association does not establish causality, it raises important concerns regarding the completeness, consistency, and accuracy of cause-of-death reporting in national mortality statistics.

A key interpretation of this finding is that the observed decline in recorded cancer mortality should be viewed with caution. In the absence of parallel improvements in diagnostic confirmation, documentation quality, and death certification practices, a decrease in officially recorded cancer deaths may not necessarily reflect a true reduction in the cancer mortality burden. Instead, it may partly reflect changes in how causes of death are documented or classified. This is particularly relevant when the decline in cancer mortality occurs alongside an increase in deaths attributed to unknown causes.

One possible explanation for this pattern is the misclassification or incomplete documentation of causes of death, particularly among patients dying outside specialized oncology settings. Errors in death certification are well documented internationally and may affect the reliability of mortality statistics, public health research, and health policy planning [10; 11]. Deaths occurring at home or in non-specialized care environments may be more likely to be registered with unspecified or unknown causes when diagnostic confirmation, medical documentation, or physician certification is limited. In such cases, cancer-related deaths may be under-recorded, contributing to an apparent decline in official cancer mortality. However, because this study used aggregated registry data, it cannot determine whether individual deaths attributed to unknown causes were in fact cancer-related.

The findings should therefore be interpreted as an indicator of a potential reporting gap rather than direct evidence of cancer mortality misclassification. The observed trend may reflect several overlapping factors,

including diagnostic uncertainty, incomplete medical records, variation in death certification practices, limited access to specialized oncology services, and differences in reporting quality across healthcare settings. The World Health Organization emphasizes that accurate medical certification of cause of death is essential for producing reliable mortality data and for improving the quality of national health statistics [1]. These factors are particularly important in end-of-life care, where patients with advanced disease may not always remain under active oncology supervision at the time of death.

Accurate mortality data are essential for public health planning, cancer control, and resource allocation. Cancer mortality statistics provide critical information for evaluating disease burden, monitoring cancer control programs, identifying service gaps, and guiding health policy decisions [3;2]. If cancer deaths are under-recorded or shifted into unknown-cause categories, the true burden of cancer may be underestimated. This can affect national cancer statistics, planning of oncology services, evaluation of cancer control programs, and estimation of the need for supportive and palliative care services. Therefore, monitoring deaths attributed to unknown causes may serve as an important quality indicator for the reliability of mortality surveillance.

The observed pattern in Georgia is also relevant in the broader context of global cancer control. Cancer remains a major global public health challenge, with approximately 20 million new cancer cases and 9.7 million cancer-related deaths estimated worldwide in 2022 [3;2]. Global projections indicate that the cancer burden will continue to increase substantially by 2050, largely due to population ageing, population growth, and changes in exposure to major risk factors [3]. In this context, reliable cause-of-death reporting is essential not only for measuring disease burden but also for identifying gaps in service delivery and ensuring that health policies are based on accurate epidemiological data.

The increase in deaths attributed to unknown causes may also be interpreted in relation to the broader problem of ill-defined or unspecified causes of death. The use of ill-defined or unknown categories reduces the informational value of mortality data and may limit the ability of health systems to accurately monitor

disease burden [12]. When a substantial number of deaths are recorded under unknown causes, mortality statistics may become less useful for planning disease-specific interventions, allocating resources, and evaluating health system performance. Therefore, reducing the proportion of unknown-cause deaths should be considered an important component of mortality data quality improvement.

The findings also have implications for palliative and end-of-life care documentation. Palliative care is defined as an approach that improves the quality of life of patients and families facing life-threatening illness through early identification, assessment, and treatment of physical, psychosocial, and spiritual problems [13]. In oncology, early integration of palliative care alongside active cancer treatment is recommended to improve patient outcomes and ensure continuity of care [7]. In the context of mortality reporting, palliative care services may also contribute to better continuity of clinical information, documentation of advanced cancer diagnoses, and more accurate certification of cause of death. However, this study cannot directly assess the role of palliative care involvement in death certification, and this relationship requires further investigation.

From a health-system perspective, the rise in deaths attributed to unknown causes may reflect broader structural challenges, including regional inequalities in access to oncology services, delayed diagnosis, limited diagnostic confirmation near the end of life, and variability in physician training related to death certification. International evidence shows that access to comprehensive cancer management and palliative care remains uneven across countries; only a minority of countries include essential cancer management and palliative care within guaranteed health benefit packages [2]. These global gaps are relevant for interpreting national mortality patterns, particularly in health systems where access to specialized services and end-of-life documentation may vary by region.

Several practical steps may improve mortality reporting accuracy. These include standardized cause-of-death certification protocols, targeted training for physicians, regular audit of death certificates, improved linkage between cancer registry and death registry data, and better documentation of cancer diagnoses across healthcare settings. Previous studies have shown that death certification errors can distort mortality statistics and reduce the usefulness of mortality data for public health decision-making [10; 11]. Particular attention should be given to deaths occurring outside hospitals, where documentation may be less complete and diagnostic confirmation may be more limited.

LIMITATIONS

This study has several limitations. First, the analysis was based on aggregated annual registry data and therefore cannot assess individual-level clinical histories, cancer types, disease stages, or exact circumstances of death. Second, the ecological design does not allow causal conclusions to be drawn. Third, deaths attributed to unknown causes may include a heterogeneous group of conditions and cannot be

assumed to represent unrecorded cancer deaths. Fourth, potential changes in coding practices, registry procedures, diagnostic access, or certification standards over time may have influenced the observed trends. Despite these limitations, the study highlights an important and underexplored pattern in national mortality data.

Future research should investigate the accuracy and completeness of cancer-related death certification in Georgia using individual-level registry linkage, medical record review, and regional comparisons. Prospective studies are also needed to examine how place of death, access to oncology care, palliative care involvement, and physician documentation practices influence cause-of-death reporting. Such evidence would help determine whether the observed increase in deaths attributed to unknown causes reflects true epidemiological change, reporting limitations, or a combination of both.

CONCLUSION

The observed decline in recorded cancer-related mortality in Georgia between 2013 and 2023, alongside a simultaneous increase in deaths attributed to unknown causes, raises important concerns about the completeness and accuracy of mortality reporting. The strong negative correlation identified between these trends suggests that cancer-related deaths may not always be consistently recorded as such, although the registry-based ecological design of this study does not allow causal conclusions to be drawn.

These findings highlight the need to strengthen quality control and standardization in cause-of-death registration. Incomplete or inaccurate recording of cancer deaths, particularly among deaths occurring outside specialized oncology settings or in contexts with limited diagnostic confirmation, may obscure the true burden of cancer mortality. Improving physician training in death certification, standardizing documentation procedures, and enhancing registry validation may contribute to more reliable mortality statistics.

Strengthening mortality surveillance, clinical documentation, and coordination between oncology, primary care, and palliative care services may improve the reliability of cancer mortality data and support more effective national cancer control planning in Georgia.

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